

Supplementary data

Bio-ethology of *Vespa crabro* in Sardinia (Italy), an area of new introduction

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Authors: Michelina Pusceddu, Matteo Lezzeri, Arturo Cocco, Ignazio Floris, Alberto Satta

Dipartimento di Agraria, Università di Sassari, Viale Italia 39A, 07100 Sassari (Italy)

Supplementary Video Captions

Video S1 *Vespa crabro* worker engaged in ventilatory activity

Video S2 Interspecific interactions between a queen of *Vespa crabro* and *Polygonia c-album*
(Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae)

Video S3 *Vespa crabro* queen processing food inside the nest

Video S4 Fifth-instar larvae of *Vespa crabro* while scratching their mandibles against the walls of its cell. In this way, the larvae produce a sound that induces hornet adults to feed them

Video S5 *Vespa crabro* worker engaged in nest building activity (Siniscola, Sardinia, Italy)

Supplementary Photo

Photo S1 Balling steps of *Apis mellifera* against *Vespa crabro*: collective defence (a), post-balling (b), and hornet removal from the nest (c)

Photo S2 Detail of the head of a fifth-instar larva of *Vespa crabro*. The mandibles used to scrape the inner cell wall, thus producing a sound that stimulates adults to feed them, are clearly visible